

PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES

DIRECTIONS FOR REGULATING THE ENVIRONMENT THAT AFFECT THE DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' SKILLS ADEQUATE TO THE CHALLENGES OF MODERN SOCIETY

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Abstract

The research shows that in the current system of socio-economic relations—the "techno-democratic information society"—the intellectual and creative activity of everyone living in it becomes a paramount requirement. For this reason, it is desirable for every member of society to rise to the level of a subject possessing intellectual skills; they must have an information culture and technological literacy.

The research presents the characteristics of "Education 4.0", which provides an effective environment for the formation of students' technological literacy and information culture, as well as the groups of intellectual skills that must be formed in this system, formulated on a certain logical basis.

The research paper highlights that these tasks are designed based on the principle of modeling the structure of various intellectual skills. As students complete them, they acquire intellectual skills such as determining the purpose of their work, systematizing educational material from this perspective, independently collecting material, etc.

The research focuses on the didactic principles necessary for the selection and systematization of tasks to be applied in order to form and develop students' technological literacy and information culture, as well as for organizing students' activities based on them.

Keywords: modern society, system of socio-economic relations, technological literacy, information culture, intellectual skills, metacognitive skills, creative thinking, idea, task.

Relevance of the topic. The characteristics of the 21st century (the modern era in which we live) require that a person develop the qualities necessary for creative activity (decision-making, problem-solving, independent learning, cooperation, teamwork, evaluating different approaches, putting forward new ideas, taking initiative, etc.), as well as the skills needed to live and progress in a rapidly changing and developing world. This creates conditions for sustainability in the future development of modern society.

In the modern era—the "techno-democratic information society"—everyone living in it must engage in intellectual and creative activity. For this, a person must rise to the level of a subject possessing technological literacy, information culture, and intellectual skills. Therefore, it is necessary to determine optimal ways to acquire technological literacy, information culture, and intellectual skills and to regulate the environment that includes such adequate approaches.

However, the methodological system for solving such a cognitive problem (of a pedagogical nature) has not been developed on a sufficiently scientific basis. Based on the above arguments, we emphasize the relevance of studying the topic "Directions for Regulating

the Environment that Affect the Development of Students' Skills Adequate to the Challenges of Modern Society."

The purpose of the study is to identify ideas about the directions for regulating the environment that affect the development of students' skills in the process of implementing general education in line with the challenges of modern society—in other words, the development of students' technological literacy, information culture, and intellectual skills.

It is taken into account that an idea is an important value: the world of human activity is always based on ideas, and everyone takes steps to verify the adequacy of the results of their activity in relation to the idea they consider acceptable.

Methodological basis of the study. In the process of conducting the research, the following served as the methodological basis: L. Bertalanffy's "Idea of System Analysis" [2;8] (an idea whose meaning is explained as an attempt to study the properties of an object based on the properties of its parts), the system-structural approach, which has been formed as an important branch of dialectics and has risen to the level of its alternative, empirical, empirical-theoretical, and theoretical methods of scientific cognition, the internal relationships of

the forms of scientific cognition, and various pedagogical and psychological research generalizations.

Interpretation of generalizations from research materials. The characteristics of modern society (the century in which we live) require that a person develop the necessary qualities for creative activity (decision-making, problem-solving, independent learning, cooperation, teamwork, evaluating different approaches, putting forward new ideas, taking initiative, etc.) in order to live and progress in a rapidly changing and developing world. This creates conditions for sustainability in the future development of society.

It is undeniable that education, which is a process of sharing human experience, has developed in stages, incorporating the characteristics of industrial revolutions, as a product of social practice (specifically, pedagogical science). The era of the Fourth Industrial Revolution requires an education system that can shape a generation that is creative, innovative, and globally competitive. Currently, the impact of the aforementioned revolution on education and the issue of the “education of the future” are being discussed on various platforms, and appropriate necessary steps are being taken. [11], [12; 92–97]

The Fourth Industrial Revolution is having an impact on the education system as well as on socio-economic spheres. In line with the industrial revolutions, “education, which is a process of sharing understanding and exchanging experience,” has developed in stages (including the specific characteristics of industrial revolutions). It is worth emphasizing that the expected paradigm shifts in the education system and the implementation of global education reforms have been further accelerated by the impact of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. [21; 147–171]

The Fourth Industrial Revolution has different implications for different areas of our lives. From this perspective, there are both opportunities and challenges for education. The use of different technologies such as IoT, 3D printing, quantum computing, artificial intelligence, etc., allows for more effective transmission of information and the development of a new “educational framework.” [14; 78–94]

It is necessary to distinguish two main reasons for the reforms carried out in the education system and its implementation system in connection with the challenges of the Fourth Industrial Revolution. The first is the training of a workforce that has the knowledge (information) and skills required to meet the needs of a rapidly changing global economy. The second is the establishment of an education and implementation system capable of producing the productive forces (labor force) necessary for the development of an adequate information society during the industrial revolution. [9; 288]

In a “techno-democratic information society,” intellectual and creative activity becomes a paramount requirement for everyone living in it. For this reason, it is desirable for every member of society to rise to the level of a subject possessing intellectual skills; they must have information culture and technological literacy. Information culture:

- is the knowledge, intellectual skills, and habits necessary for a person to adapt to the information society;

- is the ability to use the information resources and information communication tools of society;

- is the application of advanced achievements in the field of informatization and the development of information technology tools in society;

- is the ability to obtain and transmit information using modern technical means and methods, including computer technologies.

Technological literacy is the ability of people to use various digital technologies, analyze information, and operate safely in a digital environment. “This skill is not limited to using a computer and the internet, but also includes: 1. adherence to digital security and cybersecurity rules; 2. working with artificial intelligence and automation; 3. digital analytics and data processing skills; 4. using cloud technologies; 5. quickly adapting to new technologies.” [5] Technological literacy includes the ability to use information and communication technologies.

Developing digital skills is essential to ensure that individuals can safely and effectively engage with digital technologies in the future. Education systems need to take a comprehensive and holistic approach, supporting all learners in developing the skills necessary to be active and ethical users of digital technologies. [17; 57–79]

Digital education allows people to participate independently in social life. In addition, the reality of digital education and the digital revolution requires fundamental changes in the forms and methods of moral acquisition, leading to the emergence of digital skills as the most important ability. [16; 58–64] There is no doubt that developing students' digital skills will lead to their more active participation in society as digital citizens in the future. [15], [17; 57–79]

Due to the rapid development of technology, the knowledge and skills that students learn during their education become obsolete by the time they graduate. In scientific and technical education, it is necessary to educate students and prepare them for the digital environment in order to help develop and shape the use of today's fastest-growing technologies. Adapting to a rapidly changing environment will require students to engage with educational institutions even after graduation, providing both workers with updated skills and young students (and faculty) with a new perspective on the rapidly changing realities of the industrial and corporate sectors. [18; 25–30], [19; 579–592]

It is undeniable that there is specificity in the challenges of each industrial revolution. This is manifested against the background of global changes taking place in the world, and at the same time it determines the emergence of new dimensions in information culture and the content of technological literacy. At different stages of world history, humanity has faced serious changes and achieved results through the reforms carried out. In order for students to be able to demonstrate their skills and abilities in new fields emerging under the influence of the Fourth Industrial Revolution, it is necessary to implement fundamental changes in technology and taught subject programs. By reviewing the

curricula of subjects based on chemistry, biology, physics, etc., which are considered “basic sciences” in the new curricula, more attention should be paid to teaching computer science subjects, which play a key role in the formation of the literacy required for the Fourth Industrial Revolution. Naturally, greater attention should be paid to teaching these subjects. [20; 432–466]

Against the backdrop of industrial revolutions, educational program developers had to seek answers to the following fundamental questions: 1. What knowledge, skills, and values should be reflected in educational programs? 2. Will these knowledge, skills, values, and competencies form the necessary life skills in learners? 3. How can the process of implementing education be made relevant and interesting for learners? 4. How can assessment (an integral part of the process of implementing education) be made more productive and effective?

In our modern era, parameters such as relevance, practicality, effectiveness, and sustainability are the focus of attention as indicators of the quality of an educational program, while the indicator of its success is the quality of acquisition by learners and the extent to which learners can effectively use what they have acquired for their personal, social, cognitive, psychological, and emotional development.

UNESCO has the following criteria for a quality education program: the educational program must have clear objectives; meet the demands of today; be relevant to the current and future lives, experiences, desires, and aspirations of learners; aim to build a prosperous future for learners in social and economic terms, taking into account the history and culture of the country in which they live; be fair and inclusive (taking into account the individuality and individual needs of learners, etc.); be learner-centered (taking into account the needs of the learner, being appropriate to the learner's age, helping in personal development and the formation of life skills, and not overloading learners); be open and flexible (integrating emerging innovations into the content); and be consistent and relevant. [3; 5]

Education 4.0 should serve to develop the skills (intellectual skills) necessary to use new technologies that help learners develop in accordance with changes in society. It should form knowledge and skills that learners can use throughout their lives, not limited to reading and writing. Thus, the system should respond to changes in the social and economic environment in order to meet the needs of human capital. Education 4.0 aims to prepare individuals to be creative and innovative. Education should adapt to the environment in which learners live, providing them with a secure and successful future. This new system uses “smart” school management systems, learning management software, communication tools, and teaching and learning tools. [13; 238–254]

In the Education 4.0 approach, moving beyond constructivist education systems and Bloom's taxonomy, it has been determined that an environment—a teaching process—aimed at the formation and development of intellectual skills should be implemented based on the following directions: 1. 3R, which regulates understanding (Recalling, Relating, Refining); 2. 3I,

which encourages inquiry (Inquiring, Interacting, Interpreting); 3. 3P, which is based on drawing conclusions (Participating, Processing, Presenting). [22; 92–98], [23; 40–45]

Education 4.0, which provides an effective environment for the formation of intellectual skills, has the following characteristics: 1. Learning regardless of time and place (lifelong learning, e-learning, etc.); 2. The opportunity to receive personalized education according to the skills and abilities of students; 3. Taking into account the suggestions of students when preparing the curriculum; 4. The predominance of project-based learning; 5. The formation of students' ability to conduct analysis on large-scale data (Big Data); 6. Assessment of students' knowledge through the process of applying them to projects; 7. Becoming part of the education system that develops new technologies, etc. [11–12]

Scientific sources indicate that in the process of implementing general education, a student must acquire the necessary intellectual skills in order to realize his or her intellectual abilities and purposefully regulate cognitive activity. Intellectual skills are numerous. Taking into account N. A. Menchinskaya's research in this area, intellectual skills can be divided into the following groups: 1. General intellectual skills (planning, working with a book, self-control); 2. Intellectual skills necessary for the organization of mental activity (distinguishing the main idea in a text, dividing the text into parts according to meaning, comparing events, etc.); 3. Specific intellectual skills (reflecting the characteristics of a particular subject, for example, graphic skills). Another classification of intellectual skills, authored by I. Unt, is as follows: 1. Skills related to the perception of educational material (reading, observation, listening skills); 2. The ability to perform logical operations with educational material (the ability to identify what is important, compare, draw conclusions, etc.); 3. Creative skills (the ability to build a composition, etc.). [1; 60]

It is worth noting that human self-awareness has always been an urgent problem in world philosophy, psychology, and pedagogy. Scientists have approached human self-awareness from the perspective of personality, seeking its roots in the process of forming a person's ideas about his or her own “I.” Unfortunately, until recently, researchers have not sufficiently appreciated a person's understanding of the characteristics of his or her own mental world, the world of thinking, and cognitive processes. In contemporary American psychology, this issue has been brought into the spotlight and studied as a metacognitive system. It has been established that as children develop, they form certain ideas about cognitive (perception) processes and begin to regulate their own mental activity. It is worth emphasizing that self-monitoring, self-regulation, and self-assessment are metacognitive skills and are related but distinct concepts. They represent a person's awareness and understanding of the processes of self-awareness.

Flavell has studied and described in detail some of the functions of metacognition. Among them are the following: 1. Problem formulation and identification of possible solutions; 2. Knowing which cognitive processes are necessary to solve a task; 3. Activation of

cognitive rules and methods; 4. Confidence in the capabilities of thinking; 5. Attempting to solve tasks more efficiently.

These functions are interconnected. The first function is conditioned by the formation of ideas about the goals of activity in children. As they grow older, they learn to apply known methods to various situations. Gradually, students develop ideas about cognitive processes. [1; 60], [7; 74]

A system of special tasks is applied in order to form intellectual skills (determined by the requirements of the modern era) in students. These tasks are designed according to the principle of modeling the structure of various intellectual skills. As students complete them, they acquire intellectual skills such as determining the purpose of their work, systematizing educational material from this perspective, independently collecting material, writing an essay, etc. From the perspective of the principle of developmental learning, this approach is considered effective. However, in order to use it purposefully, the system and content of intellectual skills across grades and subjects must be thoroughly developed.

Tasks and their system should: be consistent with the purpose of the lesson and aimed at solving the research problem set (according to the type of thinking, information sources, form of presenting results, etc.); be appropriate to the age, knowledge and intellectual level, abilities and interests of students, and be differentiated; be based on the state program and national values; be relevant and related to real life and students' experiences; be interesting and attractive, and encourage discovery; be clearly stated; and contain clear and open questions.

It is possible for a student to act in the position of a researcher when the content of the training material and the form of action of the means and methods (in the training process, the content of the training material, the means and methods take the place of content in relation to the organizational form) are consistent with the research process. If we accept that the organizational form of training organized in accordance with the research process has a unique structure and resembles the stages of the research process, we will not have made such a serious mistake.

The following principles should be kept in focus when selecting and systematizing tasks to be applied for the purpose of forming intellectual skills and organizing students' activities based on them: completeness of the learning process; creation of equal opportunities in learning; student-centeredness; development orientation; stimulation of activity; and creation of a supportive environment.

Scientific novelty of the research. The idea of the directions of pedagogical influence aimed at the formation of students' intellectual skills in the process of implementing general education has been identified.

The theoretical significance of the study is that research on the presented topic has a special function in creating conditions for sustainability for the future development of society and in directing further scientific activity toward a broad study of theoretical and practical ways to solve the problem.

The practical significance of the research is that in the real pedagogical process, practical educators have the opportunity to benefit from the idea of the directions of pedagogical influence aimed at the formation of students' intellectual skills in their activities.

Conclusion. 1. At the modern stage of socio-economic development, the intellectual and creative activity of everyone living in the "techno-democratic information society" becomes a paramount requirement, and for this it is necessary for every member of this society to rise to the level of a subject possessing intellectual skills; 2. The existence of information culture and technological literacy in every member of a society formed in accordance with the challenges of the Fourth Industrial Revolution is a desirable quality; 3. The education system adequate to the "techno-democratic information society" has taken its place in scientific sources and pedagogical practice under the term "Education 4.0" and has been interpreted as a superstructure on logical grounds; 4. "Education 4.0," which provides an effective environment for the formation of intellectual skills, has specific characteristics, and it is possible to divide the intellectual skills that need to be formed in this system into groups on a certain logical basis; 5. In general education schools, a system of special tasks is applied to form intellectual skills in students, and it is advisable to design these tasks based on the principle of modeling the structure of various intellectual skills; 6. In selecting and systematizing tasks to be applied for the purpose of forming intellectual skills and organizing students' activities based on them, the following principles should be kept in focus: 1. Completeness of the educational process; 2. Creating equal opportunities in education; 3. Student orientation; 4. Development orientation; 5. Stimulation of activity; 6. Creating a supportive environment.

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